

IMPROVING THE METHODS OF FORMING STUDENTS' SKILLS ON MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL CONDITIONS (EXAMPLE OF GRADES 8-9)

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Annotation: Nobody can deny that we live in the innovative era, which technology is in high-demand. Therefore, the article aims at providing the solutions to the problems of forming skills in modern technology in the conditions of innovative education, not only in 8-9th grade students, but also in all students studying technology. In addition, the positive aspects of modern technologies in improving educational efficiency are also discussed

Key words: technology, innovative education, Makarenko, "collective creativity", "team skill", methodological methods.

The traditional way of education, which believes that its main task is to provide a certain amount of knowledge, is completely inadequate to prepare young people who can live in a rapidly changing world. Because science and technology are being developed to such an extent that now a person cannot keep even the most basic concepts in his memory. Moreover, if the young people who are taking independent steps in the life of constant changes are not ready for such changes both intellectually and spiritually, they may not find their place in the world of competition. Nowadays, experienced person has been accumulated in the educational system.¹

With the assistance of innovation, cleverly data is deciphered into the dialect of viable arrangements. Present day advances in instruction are

¹ Bepalko V. P. Pedagogika va o'qitishning ilg'or texnologiyalari. M.: Rossiya Mudofaa vazirligi Kasb ta'limi institutining nashriyoti, 1995 y

considered as a implies of actualizing unused educational paradigm. The patterns within the improvement of instructive advances are specifically related to the humanization of instruction and contribute to the self-awareness of the person. The term "instructive innovations" has more conceivable outcomes than "educating advances", since it moreover infers an instructive angle related to the arrangement and improvement of individual qualities of understudies. An advanced approach to educating is to construct it on innovative premise. The common standards and rules of instructing innovation are as takes after:

1. A.S. principle of pedagogical expediency formulated by Makarenko: "Not a single action of the teacher should deviate from the set goals"

2. Education and training are interconnected and as two inseparable aspects of the educational process. Teaching is the organization of pedagogically appropriate independent activities of students. The main task of the teacher, as seen by K. D. Ushinsky, is to turn the student's activity into his initiative.

3. The final concretization of the content of educational and development goals in the methodology of students' activities organized by teachers, in training manuals.

4. A necessary element of teaching technology is thematic planning, which includes a brief description of the final results and a whole chain of individual lessons connected by a single logic.

5. Organization of supervision at each stage of students' educational activities.

6. To stimulate the creative activity of students, to focus on what the student is not only capable of knowing,

7. Different forms and methods of teaching, avoiding the universalization of a particular tool or form.

Until technology advances, individual skill prevails, that is why as individual computing skills improve, "collective creativity", "team skills" develop, the concentrated expression of which is technology. The development of modern technologies in education should be carried out in accordance with the following principles²:

*The principle of integrity of technology representing the didactic system;

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*The principle of repeating technology in a certain pedagogical environment to achieve the set goals

² Guzeev V.V. Ta'limning samarali texnologiyalari: Integral va TOGIS. Moskva: Maktab texnologiyalar ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti, 2006 yil

*The principle of unevenness of pedagogical structures and the priority of factors influencing the mechanisms of self-awareness of relevant pedagogical systems;

*The principle of adapting the educational process to the personality of the student and his cognitive abilities;

The rule of potential repetition of instructive data, which makes ideal conditions for the arrangement of generalized information. The most methodological strategies of creating basic considering: 1. "Cluster" campaign; 2. Table 3. Instructive conceptualizing 4. Mental warm-up 5. Crisscross, crisscross; 6. "Embed" campaign; 7. "Bushel of thoughts" campaign; 8. "Composing Sinhwins" lobby. ³[3]

All the work carried out on the issue hence involves the forms of the project activity. Hence, with the assistance of advances, it is possible to attain enviable result (objective) within the development of individual characteristics within the handle of securing information, abilities and competencies. By utilizing modern advances within the instructive handle, dodging the conventional lesson, disposing of the dullness of the instructive environment and the equality of the instructive prepare, making conditions for changing the sorts of understudy exercises, and executing wellbeing standards which permits to extend capacity It is prescribed to select innovations depending on the substance of the subject, the objectives of the lesson, the level of planning of understudies, the capacity to meet their instructive needs, and the age gather of understudies, the lack of involvement of understudy positions can be overcome.

Currently, pedagogical technologies cover all aspects of knowledge acquisition, active learning methods, ideas, problem solving analysis, planning, evaluation and management of activity organization ideas, tools and methods. is defined as a complex inseparable process. When developing technologies, it is necessary to include activities that encourage students to be active in the educational process. Modern technologies maximally contribute to the development of students, help to choose decisions in various situations, work with information, put forward hypotheses, study processes and events, express judgments, and interact with groups in activities and positions. Only in this case, the set of educational goals can be successfully achieved. The use of active learning methods allows to change the standard communication models in the system of "teacher and student" interaction. Active learning is based on dialogic

³ "Ta'lim" ustuvor milliy loyihagini mintaqalarda amalga oshirish bo'yicha uslubiy tavsiyalar. Rossiya Federatsiyasi Ta'lim va fan vazirligi. Pedagog kadrlarning malakasini oshirish va kasbiy qayta tayyorlash akademiyasi. Moskva: 2006 yil

communication between the teacher and the student, as well as with the students themselves⁴.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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⁴ Selevko G. K. Axborot-kommunikatsiya vositalariga asoslangan pedagogik texnologiyalar. Moskva: Maktab texnologiyalari ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti, 2005 yil